

Concept of Money Laundering

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“The clampdown on money laundering and corruption is the common responsibility of all the countries in the world.” - Wang Zhaowen, spokesman for the Bank of China

There are different understandings about the emergence of money laundering in the world. One of the theories, brought by Mandinger and Zalopany, is that the history of money laundering began in England in the seventeenth century through piracy on the vessels.

Due to the high cost of maintaining a ship, such as crew, arms, ammunition and other expenses, the pirates ended up looting and robbing other ships.

Thus, the authors mentioned believed that the pirates deposited the stolen goods with respected American merchants, who traded these goods for currencies. It was believed that the integration of these values or goods would occur at the time the pirate decided to retire. With this, the pirates contributed with a true fortune that appeared to be coming from carrying out legitimate business.

The use of the expression - money laundering - seems to have been adopted in the 1920s, in the United States of America. In Lilley 's view (2001), at that time, gangs bought laundries and companies from the laundering sector, with the purpose of circulating resources, whose inflow and outflow was given at a speed adequate for the purposes of exchanging said "dirty money "for" honest money ".

Since 1986, drug trafficking has been a crime prior to money laundering and in April of that year, the OAS approved the Inter-American Program of Action of Rio de Janeiro against the use, production and trafficking of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances.

Also in 1986, the US edited the Money Laundering Act Control, typifying the conduct as criminal. However, the Vienna Convention on the Traffic in Narcotics and Substances (Vienna Convention on the Traffic in Narcotics and Drug Trafficking Psychotropic Substances in 1988 provides comprehensive measures against drug trafficking, including provisions against money laundering and the diversion of precursor chemicals. It provides for international cooperation through, for example, extradition of drug traffickers, controlled deliveries and transfer of proceedings.

It should be pointed out that money laundering in its early stages had a particular connection to the crime of toxic trafficking. It is exposed that during the Vienna Convention it is deeply concerned about the issue of drug trafficking, emphasizing that the illegal trade in toxic substances not only proves to be an alarming threat to health, but also to the foundations of the development of culture, economy and of the politics of a society, in

addition to vertiginously increasing the levels of risks that can depreciate security, stability and even state sovereignty.

As much as money laundering has been carried out since the seventeenth century, historically known as the "decade of maritime piracy", the concern with this theme has grown to a large extent in discussions of interest for the common good, starting with the Convention of Vienna of 1988.

Today the subject is debated worldwide and has been treated as a threat to the stability of the economy, due to the magnificent proportions that this crime has shaped itself by transcending the illusory barriers.

There are several denominations used in international law as translations for the expression - "money laundering", the most used are money laundering, riciclaggio del denaro, blanchiment de l'argent , laundering of assets, laundering of assets, and money laundering.

Money laundering is the process in which the criminal seeks to introduce a good, right or value arising from one of the previous crimes in legal economic activity, with the appearance of licit (recycling).

This process, as a rule, consists of three distinct stages: that of concealment, in which the criminal distances the good, right or value of criminal origin;

1- **The stage of dissimulation**, through which the object of the washing assumes the appearance of a lawful, through some kind of fraud; and

2- **The stage of reintegration**: made the concealment, the good, right or value meets conditions to be recycled, that is, reintegrated into the system, as if it were legal.

The conduct of money laundering consists of a complex of acts, a plurality of generally intricate and fractional behaviours, directed at the conversion of values and illicit goods into licit capitals and fully available to their holders.

However, it is important to emphasize the concept of money laundering as an activity, that is, the performance of acts that are concatenated in time and space, in order to achieve a certain purpose. These chained actions are concealment, concealment, and integration. In view of the above, it is stated that money laundering would be the set of operations whose purpose is to incorporate goods, rights and values, originating in crime, into the economy, in the form of licit capital.

The concept of the money-laundering phases assumes that: To disguise illicit profits without compromising those involved, money laundering takes place through a dynamic process that requires:

- first, distancing funds from their source, avoiding an association direct them with the crime;

- second, the disguise of its various movements to hinder the tracing of these resources; and third, making money available again to criminals after having been sufficiently busy in the wash cycle and being able to be considered clean.

Common feature of these crimes is that they often reach social interests and almost always generate large amounts of illicit money. In short, the process of laundering unlawfully obtained capital by criminal organizations consists in placing, concealing the criminal proceeds of assets or values and integrating them into the economy, giving the money an appearance of legal origin, beyond suspicion.

After the three phases have occurred, there is a complete recycling, where permanent procedures to erase the traces of illicit money happen, after the conversion of "dirty money" into fully licit goods and thus defined as "washes". In this way, the most used mechanisms in the money laundering process will theoretically involve three fundamental stages of the whole process that are totally independent and often occur simultaneously.

- The first stage of the process is the placement of money in the country's economic system, aiming to conceal its illicit origin in view of the lower visibility, where the criminal executes money movements in countries with more permissive rules and in those that can thus be countries that have "Off Shores".

The assignment will take place through the following means: full or fractional deposits, purchase of negotiable instruments or purchase of goods.

To make it difficult to identify the origin of money, criminals apply sophisticated and increasingly dynamic techniques, such as the smurfing method, which is the fractionation of the values that transit through the financial system and the use of commercial establishments that usually work with cash, as well as jewellery markets, exchange houses, travel agencies and factories

- The second stage of the money laundering process is concealment. Concealment consists of sending money through various financial transactions to change its format and make it difficult to track.

Concealment can be done through various transfers from one bank to another; electronic transfers between various accounts of different people in different countries; making deposits and withdrawals in order to change account balances; currency exchange and purchase of expensive items as well as boats, houses, cars, diamonds, gold, among others, in order to change the form of money. It is the most complex phase of the laundering scheme, and its purpose is to break the chain of evidence before the possibility of conducting investigations into the origin of money.

Criminals seek to move it electronically, transferring the assets to anonymous accounts - preferably in countries covered by banking secrecy law - or making deposits in "ghost" accounts.

The preferred areas to apply illicit money, at this stage, are hotels, churches and institutions that live on donations, in short, every sector where complexity is precisely the difficulty of gauging a direction.

- The final step of the money laundering scheme is integration. As the term implies, integration is when profits and goods are reinserted into the legal economy without raising suspicion or giving them a legitimate source of appearance.

Thus, at this stage, money is reincorporated into the financial system in a legitimate way - transferring the image of a currency from legal transactions. This can be done through a bank transfer to the account of a local company in which the criminal "invests" in exchange for profit sharing; of the sale of a yacht purchased during the concealment phase.

At this stage, the criminal can use the money without being caught in the act. It is very difficult to catch a criminal during the integration phase if there is no documentation during the previous phases.

Some areas of the economy are targeted to be part of the money laundering procedure. Among the most sought after sectors are financial institutions.

Since they are one of the main focuses of the most diverse criminals for the practice of money laundering, financial institutions have become the target of international organizations, which have stipulated various regulations, agreements and recommendations, in order to prevent and inhibit the use of these institutions in the practice of the laundering of illicit financial resources.

In this context, mention is made of the Basel agreement and the resulting rules (Basel I and Basel II) and the 40 FATF recommendations against money laundering and terrorist financing, published in 1990 and revised in 2003.

The Basel Core Principles comprise 25 Core Principles, which are indispensable for a truly effective supervisory system. The Principles concern: Preconditions for effective banking supervision - Principle 1; Authorizations and structure - Principles 2 to 5; Prudential regulations and requirements - Principles 6 to 15; Methods of continuous banking supervision - Principles 16 to 20; Information requirements - Principle 21; Formal powers of supervisors - Principle 22, and International banking activities - Principles 23 to 25.